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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the deliverable ***D3.2 Functional Architecture Design Document*** which describes the functional design of the HELMET architecture with focus on the functional architecture solutions for the augmentation network subsystem as well as the general architecture solution for the onboard subsystem for each transportation segments (Railway, automotive and UAV segments).

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CONTRIBUTING PARTNER	2
DISTRIBUTION LIST	2
APPROVAL STATUS	2
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
Table of Contents	4
List of Figures.....	6
List of Tables	7
Definition and abbreviations.....	8
1. Introduction.....	9
2. Functional Design of the Augmentation Integrity Monitoring Network.....	10
2.1 Reference Stations Data Gateway.....	12
2.2 Communication Front-End	13
2.3 SIS & RS FDE.....	14
2.4 RTK/NRTK Augmentation Messages Calculation & Formatting	17
2.5 Ancillary Data gateway	18
2.6 Reference Framework Definition	19
3. Functional architecture Design for RailWay MOBU Navigation Unit.....	21
3.1 FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE FOR ARCHITECTURE_1	21
3.1.1 GNSS AUGMENTATION & INTEGRITY MONITORING.....	21
3.1.2 GNSS RECEIVER.....	21
3.1.3 GNSS CORRECTION	22
3.1.4 GNSS FDE	22
3.1.5 TRACK DIGITAL MAP.....	23
3.1.6 ESTIMATION COMPUTER.....	23
3.1.7 INTEGRITY MONITORING.....	23
3.2 FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE FOR ARCHITECTURE 2	23
3.2.1 GNSS AUGMENTATION & INTEGRITY MONITORING.....	24
3.2.2 GNSS RECEIVER.....	24
3.2.3 GNSS CORRECTION	24
3.2.4 MULTISENSOR FDE	24
3.2.5 TRACK DIGITAL MAP.....	25
3.2.6 ESTIMATION COMPUTER.....	25
3.2.7 INTEGRITY MONITORING.....	25

4. Functional architecture Design for Automotive MOBU Navigation Unit	26
4.1 Communication module	26
4.2 GNSS Positioning module	27
4.3 Multi-sensor localization module	28
4.4 Integrity monitoring module	29
5. Functional architecture Design for UAV MOBU Navigation Unit	31
5.1 Introduction	31
5.2 Helmet UAV system architecture and system functional design considerations	31
5.3 UAV positioning main subsystems functional design	41
5.3.1 OBU	41
5.3.2 PIT station	63
6. References	71

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: General design flow	9
Figure 2: Overview of different design levels and their dependency	10
Figure 3: Reference Stations Data Gateway Functional Architecture	13
Figure 4: Communication Front-End Functional Architecture	14
Figure 5: 2-Tiers Algorithm Process flow.....	15
Figure 6: Satellite And Reference Station FDE functional Architecture.....	17
Figure 7: Augmentation Messages Calculation & Formatting	18
Figure 8: Ancillary Data Processing Function.....	19
Figure 9: Reference Framework Definition functional Architecture	20
Figure 10: Functional architecture for ARCHITECTURE_1	21
Figure 11: Functional architecture for ARCHITECTURE_2	24
Figure 12 Functional Design of MOBU for Automobile	26
Figure 13: Overall UAV application system architecture.....	31
Figure 14: UAV Rail scenario with operational area constrained by virtual fences.....	32
Figure 15: UAV reference mission timeline and its operative modes.	33
Figure 16: Landing autonomous by optical support principle of operations.....	34
Figure 17: Critical Condition report flow	43
Figure 18: UOBU and associated navigation function block diagram	44
Figure 19: Avionic integrated integrity functional block diagram according to ABIA principle and legacy standard ARAIM.	45
Figure 20: OBU operative modes.....	46
Figure 21: GMI operation example.....	46
Figure 22: possible combination of OBU sensor operations	47
Figure 23: PVT subsystem functional block diagram.....	48
Figure 24: interference detection.....	50
Figure 25: COTS GNSS receiver also with embedded IMU	51
Figure 26: integrity functional block diagram	53
Figure 27: overall avionic based integrity functional system interfaces.....	53
Figure 28: integrity and FDIR computation process on board.....	54
Figure 29: thresholds definition for caution and warning flags	55
Figure 30: optical processing subsystem functional block diagram	56
Figure 31: the innovative Wide FOV camera proposed for this study.	57
Figure 32: Polifemo demonstrator characteristics.....	58
Figure 33: conceptual system based on two WFOV cameras with integrated the GNSS antenna on the top and HR lens on the bottom for optical navigation assistance.....	58
Figure 34: optical processing imaging	59
Figure 35: image processing for landing	60
Figure 36: UAV Communication model	61
Figure 37: Communication subsystem block diagram	62
Figure 38: ADS-B equipment for UAV on the left; complete DDA sensor suit on the right	63
Figure 39: PIT station functions.....	64
Figure 40: PIT station functional block diagram.....	65
Figure 41: determination of UAV heading by combined processing of PIT station and on board GNSS Rx	66

Figure 42: OBU configuration based on to similar computers.....	67
Figure 43: OBU configuration based on two parallel computers and a controller.....	68
Figure 44: FTA based on the PVT computation modes.....	69
Figure 45: OBU- PVT FTA.	69
Figure 46: OBU HW FTA	70
Figure 47: DDA FTA	70

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Requirements allocation to functional blocks.....	10
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DEFINITION AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
A	Availability
AIMN	Augmentation and Integrity Monitoring Network
ARAIM	Advanced Receiver Autonomous Integrity Monitor
ATP	Along Track Position / Positioning
ATPL	Along Track Protection Level
BTM	Balise Transmission Module
CCF	Common Cause Failure
CENELEC	Comité Européen de Normalisation Électrotechnique
CCS	Control Command and Signalling
CCS TSI	Control Command and Signalling Technical Specifications for Interoperability
CMD	Cold Movement Detector / Detection
CONOPS	Concept of Operations
DHD	Double Heading Differences
E/E/PE	<i>Electric/Electronic/Programable Electronic</i>
EGNOS	European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service, i.e. European SBAS
EGNSS	European GNSS
EMI	Electro-magnetic interference
ERA	The <i>European Union Agency</i> for Railways
ERTMS	European Rail Traffic Management System
ESA	European Space Agency
ETCS	European Train Control System
EU	European Union
EVC	<i>European Vital Computer</i>
FFR	Functional Failure Rate
FOG	Fibre Optic Gyroscope
FR	Failure Rate
FTA	Fault tree Analysis
Galileo	European GNSS
GBAS	Ground Based Augmentation System
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GNSS MI	GNSS Misleading Information
GNSS SIS	GNSS Signal-in-Space
GNSS SoL	GNSS Safety of Life (service)

1. INTRODUCTION

In the present deliverable D3.2 we develop a functional design of the multimodal positioning and localization system based on the high-level design presented in deliverable D3.1 (see general design flow in Figure 1). During the development special care is taken to provide a system design which will eventually fulfil the system requirements specified in D2.3 (revised in D3.1).

Figure 1: General design flow

The multimodal positioning and localization system is designed to operate in three different application segments (Railway, automated car and UAV segments). Each vehicle localization system consists of different subsystems, i.e. the Augmentation Subsystem, Communication Subsystem and the On-board Subsystem. Figure 2 shows again the different hierarchies of our architecture. The Augmentation subsystem is identical for all three application segments while the communication subsystem and the On-board subsystem are tailored to each application. In the following sections we will therefore describe the functional design of the Augmentation subsystem (section 2) and three version of the On-board subsystem function design (section 3, 4 & 5).

Figure 2: Overview of different design levels and their dependency

2. FUNCTIONAL DESIGN OF THE AUGMENTATION INTEGRITY MONITORING NETWORK

The functional analysis starts with the allocation of requirements to main functional blocks defined in D3.1. The allocation is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Requirements allocation to functional blocks

ID	Name	Description	Functional Blocks
SR-AUG-OPE-001	Augmentation System Fault Detection and Exclusion THR	The Augmentation System Fault Detection and exclusion for RTK and NRTK has to be based on the 2-Tiers Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SIS & RS FDE
SR-AUG-PER-002	Augmentation System THR	The Augmentation System has to guarantee a THR of $5E10^{-7}/h$ for RTK and NRTK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SIS & RS FDE RTK/NRTK Augmentation Messages Calculation & Formatting
SR-AUG-FUN-003	Augmentation messages contents	The Augmentation System performs SIS and Reference Stations Fault Detection and Exclusion for RTK and NRTK. Constellation, satellites and Reference Stations Faults are detected and excluded. A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SIS & RS FDE RTK/NRTK Augmentation Messages Calculation & Formatting

		constellation, satellite and Reference Station Healthy mask is transmitted to the OBU for the needed relevant exclusion	
SR-AUG-INF-004	Standardised Augmentation System Protocol and Format for accuracy augmentation messages	The Augmentation system has to transmit Augmentation messages through RTCM NTRIP protocol and RTCM SC-104 standard (latest issue) for not integrity messages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication Front-End
SR-AUG-INF-005	Not Standardised Augmentation System Protocol and Format for accuracy augmentation messages	The Augmentation system has to transmit and log the Augmentation messages for integrity through RTCM NTRIP protocol and RTCM SC-104 and RTCM SC-134 data fields and messages to be defined using existing data types	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication Front-End • Ancillary Data Gateway
SR-FUN-AUG-006	Augmentation to Service Level allocation	The Augmentation system to service level allocation is reported in Table 5 of D3.1 deliverable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIS & RS FDE • RTK/NRTK Augmentation Messages Calculation & Formatting • Ancillary Data Gateway • SSR Data Processing • Reference Framework Definition
SR-AUG-OPE-008	RTK Augmentation maximum service coverage	The Service Coverage for RTK Fixed solution is 30 km	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reference Station geographical distribution
SR-AUG-OPE-009	NRTK Augmentation Reference Stations distribution	At least 4 Reference Station, distributed in a polygon with maximum edges length of 70 Km and including the demonstration area, have to be provided for implementing the NRTK service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reference Station geographical distribution
SR-AUG-OPE-010	2-Tiers connection to EDAS	The Augmentation control Centre has to be connected to	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International Organisations

		the EDAS system for gathering RIMS raw data through RTCM SC-104 data format and NTRIP protocol for implementing the 2-Tiers Algorithm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIS & RS FDE
SR-AUG-OPE-011	Augmentation Centre Service Mountpoints	The Augmentation Control Centre provide messages for each Service Levels through distinct RTCM NTRIPCaster mountpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication Front-End
SR-AUG-OPE-012	Augmentation correction messages update rate	The Augmentation Control Centre provides correction messages to an update rate of 1Hz or 10 Hz	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RTK/NRTK Augmentation Messages Calculation & Formatting • Communication Front-End
SR-AUG-OPE-013	2-Tiers Probability of missed detection	The 2-Tiers Probability of missed detection for the Augmentation System and the SIS is set to 1e-4 or 1e-3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIS & RS FDE

The starting point for the requirements analysis is the Safety Analysis carried out within D2.3 and D3.1.

In order to implement the accuracy service levels, RTK and NRTK calculation functions are implemented.

The functional analysis is carried out in the following.

2.1 REFERENCE STATIONS DATA GATEWAY

This function has to gather Reference Station data and pass them to the internal Augmentation functions.

The functional architecture is reported in Figure 3

Figure 3: Reference Stations Data Gateway Functional Architecture

An NTRIP Client module is in charge of connecting the Augmentation Control Centre to the single Reference Stations Networks NTRIP Casters for gathering raw data streams. Raw data are therefore sent to the NRTK or PPP processing modules or directly to the NTRIPCaster for relevant broadcasting. All internal communication are performed through RTCM SC104 v3.3 data formats.

2.2 COMMUNICATION FRONT-END

The communication Front-End has to implement the following main functions:

- User Receiver Augmentation request
- Routing of the Request to the Augmentation Calculation and Formatting
- Adaptation of messages to specific application domain formats

It has to be emphasized that the basic protocol and data format structure for the Augmentation Network is the currently most implemented standard into receivers, e.g. RTCM NTRIP protocol and RTCM SC104 v3.3 ([1] [2]). Limited adaptations can be implemented, in order to allow the interfacing with single application domain communication infrastructures. The definition of such adaptation functions will not be implemented within HELMET. It will follow the development of standard, as RTCM SC-134 Committee output.

The functional architecture of the Communication Front-End is showed in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Communication Front-End Functional Architecture

The Gateway implementation through an NTRIPCaster functionality. It accepts user receiver connection request and routes them to the Augmentation Messages Calculation & formatting function.

The Augmentation messages are generated and sent to the Multimodal Adaptation Layer.

The adaptation layer gets the identified User Application class and performs the adaptation of the message to the single application domain.

The adapted messages are therefore sent to the NTRIPCaster for the transmission to the user.

2.3 SIS & RS FDE

This function is in charge of implementing the Fault Detection and Exclusion for GNSS (SIS and Reference Stations).

The implemented algorithm is based on the 2-Tiers approach [3]. It is based on two phases:

1. Satellite exclusion
2. Reference Station exclusion

Figure 5: 2-Tiers Algorithm Process flow

The FDE for satellite exclusion is based on the calculation of Single Differences residuals among satellites and the comparison with a statistical derived threshold. It is defined as a function of the probability of false alert or probability of missed detection, following the Neyman-Pearson criterion.

The Single difference residual is defined as:

$$\zeta^i(k) = \tilde{\mathbf{S}}^{(i)} \Delta \rho_{Tier2}(k) \quad (1)$$

The single difference between satellites, taking l as the pivot satellite, where $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}^i$ is the differencing operator and $\Delta \rho_{Tier2}$ is the measurement residual at epoch k .

The test statistic is represented by the weighted squared norm of single differences residuals:

$$\tilde{y}_{cod}^i = \left[\zeta^i(k) \right]^T \mathbf{R}_{\zeta^i}^{-1} \zeta^i(k) \quad (2)$$

where R_{ζ^i} is the covariance matrix of single differenced measurements.

A satellite is excluded if the above residuals passes a defined threshold $\gamma_{y_{cod}^i}$.

The same approach is used for the Exclusion of Reference Stations, where double difference among satellites and Reference station are applied for the residual calculation.

$$z_{cod,n} = \left[\xi_{n,Tier1}(k) \right]^T \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_{\xi_{n,Tier1}}^{-1} \xi_{n,Tier1}(k) \quad (3)$$

Where

$$\xi_{n,Tier1}(k) = \mathbf{S} \mathbf{D}_{(N_{RIM_1}+1)}^{(1)} \Delta \mathbf{p}_{raw}(k) \quad (4)$$

Is the vector of double difference residuals, calculated through the differences operator S and D. The probability of excluding the n-th healthy Reference Integrity Monitoring Station while it is healthy is provided by:

$$P_{FE,z_n}^{RIM} = 1 - D_{G\chi_{N_z}^2} \left(\gamma_{z_n}^i; \tilde{\Lambda}_{z_n}^i \right) \quad (5)$$

where $\Lambda_{z_n}^i$ is the vector of the eigenvalues of $\mathbf{R}_{\xi_{n,Tier1}}$ and

$$D_{G\chi_n^2}(x; \Lambda) = \frac{1}{\prod_{i=2}^n \Lambda_2} D_{\chi_1^2} \left(\frac{x}{\Lambda_1} \right) * P_{\chi_1^2} \left(\frac{x}{\Lambda_2} \right) * \dots * P_{\chi_1^2} \left(\frac{x}{\Lambda_n} \right) \quad (6)$$

Is the cumulative generalised Chi-Square distribution.

Given the Probability of False exclusion as a design parameter, the inversion of (5) allows determining the threshold for the comparison.

The same approach can be followed for determining the threshold for satellites and Reference Station through the Probability of Missed Detection, applying the value reported in the System Requirement SR-AUG-OPE-013. This values, together with SR-AUG-PER-002 and the relevant Augmentation Fault Tree Analysis, allows meeting the Augmentation requirements.

The FDE functional decomposition is reported in Figure 6.

Taking the Reference Station raw data, the weighted norm of residuals is calculated.

The output of this function are the Satellite and Reference Stations Integrity Masks to passed to the RTK/NRTK Augmentation Messages Calculation & Formatting for relevant resources exclusion.

The same algorithm has been demonstrated to be effective also for antispoofing implementation.

Figure 6: Satellite And Reference Station FDE functional Architecture

2.4 RTK/NRTK AUGMENTATION MESSAGES CALCULATION & FORMATTING

The Augmentation Messages calculation is performed in different ways, depending on the implemented Augmentation system.

- **RTK:** Reference Station quality is checked, relevant raw data formatted in a RTCM v3.3. message format and sent to the Communication Front-end for Broadcasting. If NEAREST modality is implemented, the received user position allows selecting the closest Reference Station to the user (Implemented in the project)
- **NRTK:** Reference Station quality is checked, relevant Double Difference in the Network calculated, Network Ambiguity solved and a Virtual Reference Station created close to the user, allowing a sparser Reference Station network implementation. The VRS method implies the reception of the approximate user position from the Communication Front-End (implemented in the project)
- **SSR:** through the elaboration of Reference Stations raw data, precise estimation of orbits and clock corrections is calculated and transmitted to the user for PPP implementation. PPP-AR techniques can be also implemented (PPP and PPP-AR are not implemented in this HELMET Project)

The functional Architecture of the RTK/NRTK Augmentation Messages Calculation & Formatting is showed in Figure 7. Reference Station selection can be performed at Communication Front-end level for sake of efficiency.

Ionosphere errors interpolation close to the user position is implemented through the Co-location Method.
Faulty satellite and Reference Stations, determined by the FDE function, are excluded from the computation.

Figure 7: Augmentation Messages Calculation & Formatting

2.5 ANCILLARY DATA GATEWAY

This function is in charge of collecting ancillary data for extended functionalities implementation. Within the HELMET project, the following options are explored:

- Tropospheric errors estimations collection and broadcasting: Pressure, Humidity and Temperature can be collected from on-board sensors and relevant ZTD through the Saastamoinen model [4], calculated in a grid or interpolated way for sharing with other users. Pressure, Humidity and Temperature have to be weighted through the declared sensor precision for taking into account different resolutions and accuracies

- Cadastral Reference Points Coordinates: Closest Cadastral Reference points coordinates, as present into institutional Databases, are sent to the user, depending on the approximate position, for future sensor fusion algorithms implementation

The functional architecture of the component is reported in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Ancillary Data Processing Function

2.6 REFERENCE FRAMEWORK DEFINITION

The Reference Framework is calculated through Network Adjustment performed on the Reference Station used for the Pilot and the surrounding EUREF Reference Station.

Reference Stations are selected, in the case of multiple Reference Stations and NRTK implementation, in order to meet the requirement SR-AUG-OPE-009.

The Network Adjustment, following EUREF and National network processing guidelines, leads to determine ETRF2000 and IGS14 coordinates.

Scientific Software is used for the processing.

The functional Architecture of the Reference Framework Definition function is showed in Figure 9.

RINEX files at 30s sampling rate are gathered from the Reference Stations to be processed, as well as needed ancillary data (ocean loading files, precise ephemeris and clock corrections, EUREF and IGS Reference Stations coordinates, receivers and antenna data).

A file of selected EUREF and Reference Stations around the ones to be used for the project are previously selected.

After a preliminary raw data quality check, a first precise solution is derived (without ambiguity fixing) at decimetre level.

Therefore, a daily Network Least Square adjustment is performed and Reference Stations coordinates derived.

At the end, 7 days solutions are further adjusted and combined for obtaining the weekly solution.

Due to the link of EUREF2000 to the EURASIA plaque, the velocities of the References Stations and relevant coordinates drift are very low during the project duration and can be considered negligible.

Figure 9: Reference Framework Definition functional Architecture

3. FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE DESIGN FOR RAILWAY MOBU NAVIGATION UNIT

In this section, we briefly describe the functional architecture for Railway MOBU. The analysis hereafter shown refers to deliverable D3.1 (High-Level Design Document) where two different architectures are proposed for the railway application: ARCHITECTURE_1 and ARCHITECTURE_2.

3.1 FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE FOR ARCHITECTURE_1

The Figure 10 shows the functional architecture for the ARCHITECTURE_1 introduced for Along Track Position determination. The definition of this functional architecture is based on the high level scheme presented in the par. 6.1.1 and on the block diagram of the architecture_1 in the par. 8.2 of the document D3.1 (High-Level Design Document).

Figure 10: Functional architecture for ARCHITECTURE_1

3.1.1 GNSS AUGMENTATION & INTEGRITY MONITORING

The GNSS AUGMENTATION & INTEGRITY MONITORING block through the COMMUNICATION subsystem, provides to the RAIL MOBU the augmentation and integrity information during the operation of the entire system. In the HELMET project, the system can operate according to the service level defined in the documents D2.3 (SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS SPECIFICATION): SL1, SL2, SL3 and SL4. Specifically, the augmentation system participates to providing of these service levels (SL) operating in different way: differential mode and RTK/NRTK mode. Therefore, the augmentation information broadcasts from this block to the MOBU are the differential correction for the first operative mode and the GNSS raw data for the second one.

3.1.2 GNSS RECEIVER

In the RAIL MOBU functional architecture, the GNSS receiver is a sensor. It is considered as a black box able to provide the necessary data to perform the GNSS fault detection and exclusion (FDE)

and the GNSS correction functionalities. The data that must be available in output to the receiver are the GNSS raw data (pseudorange, carrier phase, Doppler and CN0) and the I/Q samples of the received Signal-In-Space (SIS) after the analog-to-digital converter (ADC).

3.1.3 GNSS CORRECTION

The goal of the GNSS correction functionality is the application of the corrections coming from the augmentation system to the GNSS raw data provided by the receiver. In addition to that, an integrity mask is applied by exploiting the information sent by the monitoring network. The expected output is the GNSS raw data for the healthy satellites.

3.1.4 GNSS FDE

The GNSS FDE functionality carries out the fault detection and exclusion on the GNSS raw data. In particular, this functionality can be logically decomposed in the following sub-functions:

- Multipath/EMI anomaly detection
- Measurements consistency check
- MP/EMI MAP
- MP/EMI map manager
- GNSS exclusion

MULTIPATH/EMI ANOMALY DETECTION

The Multipath/EMI anomaly detection function is responsible for the identification of local threat such as multipath and electromagnetic interference. These functionalities are implemented at pre-correlation level using the I/Q data available in output of the analog-to-digital convert of the GNSS receiver. The EMI and Multipath detection logic provides binary outputs that give information about the presence or not of interference for each frequency band considered.

MEASUREMENTS CONSISTENCY CHECK

The measurements consistency check functionality has to check the consistency of the measurements coming from a given GNSS receiver after the correction and integrity information are applied. The aim of the component is to evaluate, for each epoch and for each satellite, if the set of measurements is reliable. The check is performed at the post-correlation level.

MP/EMI MAP

The MP/EMI map is a database that contains the information related to the presence of multipath and electromagnetic interference along line. Particularly, a set of relevant points is identified within the track area. Two binary flags are associated to each relevant point.

MULTIPATH/EMI MAP MANAGER

The multipath/EMI map manager is a functionality in charge of the access to MP/EMI map database. Particularly, it manages all the authorization and authentication process needed for the security. Moreover, this entity guarantees the bidirectional access to the database for the updating and the use of the maps. The access to the map is performed by means of the PVT estimation.

GNSS EXCLUSION

The GNSS exclusion functionality is responsible of excluding the faulty data from the estimation process taken into account the detection information provided by the measurements consistency check and Multipath/EMI anomaly detection and integrity monitoring functionalities. At same time,

the output is used in the estimation computer. This information is available outdoor through the integrity monitoring functionality.

3.1.5 TRACK DIGITAL MAP

The track digital map is a database containing the description of the railway line. Particularly, the line is composed by a set of track portion. Each portion is represented by a set of relevant points. For each point, the stored information contains the absolute coordinates in ECEF Cartesian frame and the relative mileage from a significant point for the railway scenario.

3.1.6 ESTIMATION COMPUTER

The estimation computer function is responsible of computing the position, velocity and time solution using several information. Specifically, the information is:

- Track IDs information: it is the IDs list of the track portions that defines the route along which the train moves from starting to the arriving stations;
- Line information from the track digital map module (the relevant line portion can be identified through the track IDs described in previous bullet);
- GNSS raw data from GNSS FDE module;
- GNSS raw data and integrity augmentation from reference stations that constitute the augmentation and integrity monitoring network (AIMN);
- Integrity information from the integrity monitoring module.

3.1.7 INTEGRITY MONITORING

The integrity monitoring functionality is in charge of monitoring the healthy status of the solution. The integrity check is made in position domain and at this process participates the GNSS FDE functionality with a continuously exchange of integrity information and the estimation computer functionality providing the PVT solution. The outputs are the trusted position solution, the protection level and the integrity information coming from the GNSS FDE as feedback information for the end user of the entire integrity process.

3.2 FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE FOR ARCHITECTURE 2

The Figure 11 shows the functional architecture for ARCHITECTURE_2 introduced for Track Identification function. The definition of this functional architecture is based on the high level architecture presented in the par. 6.1.1 and on the block diagram of the architecture_2 in the par. 8.2 of the document D3.1 (High-Level Design Document).

Some functional blocks are the same of the homologues blocks of the ARCHITECTURE_1 presented in the 3.1. For these blocks we just refer to the proper section.

Figure 11: Functional architecture for ARCHITECTURE_2

3.2.1 GNSS AUGMENTATION & INTEGRITY MONITORING

This functional block is the homologue of the GNSS AUGMENTATION & INTEGRITY MONITORING of the ARCHITECTURE_1. Please refer to the section 3.1.1.

3.2.2 GNSS RECEIVER

This functional block is the homologue of the GNSS RECEIVER of the ARCHITECTURE_1. Please refer to the section 3.1.2.

3.2.3 GNSS CORRECTION

This functional block is the homologue of the GNSS CORRECTION of the ARCHITECTURE_1. Please refer to the section 3.1.3.

3.2.4 MULTISENSOR FDE

The MULTISENSOR FDE functionality carries out the fault detection and exclusion on the raw data of the sensors involved in the position estimation process such as GNSS receiver, IMU, LIDAR, and IMAGING. In particular, this functionality can be logically decomposed in the following sub-functions:

- GNSS FDE
- Measurements consistency check
- Multisensor exclusion

GNSS FDE

This functional block is the homologue of the GNSS FDE of the ARCHITECTURE_1. Please refer to the section 3.1.4.

MEASUREMENTS CONSISTENCY CHECK

The MEASUREMENTS CONSISTENCY CHECK functionality has to check the consistency of the measurements coming from sensors. The aim of this component is to evaluate if the set of measurements available at given epoch is coherent with the previous story considering factors such as vehicle dynamic, environmental factors and sensor characteristics.

MULTISENSOR EXCLUSION

The MULTISENSOR EXCLUSION functionality is responsible of excluding the faulty data from the estimation process taken into account the information provided by the GNSS FDE and the measurements consistency check functions carried out on the measures of the other sensors. At the same time, the output is used by the estimation computer. This information is available outdoor through the integrity monitoring functionality.

3.2.5 TRACK DIGITAL MAP

This functional block is the homologue of the TRACK DIGITAL MAP of the ARCHITECTURE_1. Please refer to the section 3.1.5.

3.2.6 ESTIMATION COMPUTER

The estimation computer function is responsible of computing the position, velocity and time solution using several information and select the track Id of the line portion on which the train is lying on in a given time. Specifically, the information is:

- Line information from the track digital map module (the relevant line portion can be identified through the track IDs described in previous bullet);
- GNSS raw data from multisensor FDE module;
- GNSS raw data and integrity augmentation from reference stations that constitute the augmentation and integrity monitoring network (AIMN);
- Integrity information from the integrity monitoring module.

3.2.7 INTEGRITY MONITORING

The integrity monitoring functionality is in charge of monitoring the healthy status of the solution. The integrity check is made in position domain and at this process participates the MULTISENSOR FDE functionality with a continuously exchange of integrity information and the estimation computer functionality providing the PVT solution. The outputs are both trusted position solution and the Track ID, the protection level and the integrity information coming from the MULTISENSOR FDE as feedback information for the end user of the entire integrity process.

messages from road-side infrastructures”, which are intuitively in charge of the functions of the radio front-end processing for the communication links.

From the navigation system safety point of view, if the communication module fails during operation, the augmentation data and the GNSS integrity monitoring data provided by the AIMN, or the road-side infrastructure information will become unavailable to the automobile. The missing of augmentation data and integrity information from AIMN will degrade the performance of the GNSS receiver from both the aspect of accuracy and the aspect of integrity. The lack of the road-side infrastructure information will affect the multi-sensor positioning and localization performance. Nevertheless, due to the robustness and redundancy provided by the multiple sensor approach, the MOBU can still generate meaningful positioning and localization results if the other functions are nominal. However, the vehicle may need to adjust the operational mode accordingly after detecting the communication function failure, so that the reliability of the navigation solution can be retained to the most extent, even though the achievable performance might be reduced. The malfunctions for the communication function can be due to hardware or system failure in the communication subsystem onboard, or can be temporary performance degeneration caused by the environmental factors, e.g., block of signals by physical structures, or communication channel issues such as interference and fading. The failures in the communication module can be detected by monitoring and validating the received signals and messages.

4.2 GNSS PROCESSING MODULE

GNSS receiver is the core sensor in the positioning function of the MOBU for automobile. It is arguably the only sensor that can deliver absolute position in general. The GNSS processing module contains the functions that are necessary to generate position estimates by using the GNSS receiver. The module is marked by purple color in the diagram.

In the functional design diagram, the block “Get GNSS measurements” contains the GNSS signal sensing as well as the receiver processing procedures including GNSS radio frontend signal processing, signal acquisition, tracking using tracking loops, etc. As a result, the function block provides the GNSS pseudorange and carrier phase measurements to the other part of the MOBU system.

The GNSS measurements are passed to the function block “Validate and correct measurements” (after passing through some threat detection for better performance, which will be mentioned later). Intuitively, the function validates and removes errors in the input measurements for estimation algorithms by exploiting the information from AIMN.

From the safety aspects, the failure of the GNSS processing module will lead to the effect that one or several of the GNSS measurements are affected by unbounded errors or an absolute positioning solution from GNSS cannot be provided. Similarly, as mentioned in the communication module, the cause of the GNSS processing failure can also be either systematic such as hardware faults or environmental, e.g., the satellite signals are blocked when the car drives into a tunnel or an urban canyon. When the GNSS failure happens, the vehicle needs to take operations depending on the situation, i.e., either changing to different operational modes that relies on different positioning algorithms or other sensors for short time, or trigger alarms and take emergency operations.

4.3 MULTI-SENSOR LOCALIZATION MODULE

Compared with the GNSS-only based navigation solution, the multi-sensor set-up provides the automobile MOBU redundancies and reliability against single point failures, which is significantly important for this safety critical application. The multi-sensor localization module provides the functions to estimate the vehicle's position by exploiting the measurements from multiple sensors, and to localize the vehicle in the map of surrounding environments.

In the functional design diagram, there are a few blocks belonging to the multi-sensor localization module, which are marked by blue color. Among them, there are four blocks with the function to acquire measurements and data from different sensors or data sources, which are respectively: "Get kinematic measurements", "Get optical measurements", "Get road-side messages and measurements", and "Get local map data".

The function "Get kinematic measurements" outputs the vehicle kinematic measurements from sensors such as IMU and wheel odometer of the automobile. Instead of determining absolute position, the kinematic measurements provide the relative motion information of the vehicle between different time slots. In addition, the IMU can provide orientation information, which cannot be achieved easily by using GNSS receivers.

The function "Get optical measurements" outputs measurements from optical sensors such as camera and LIDAR. The optical sensors can estimate the six degrees-of-freedom relative motion (3D rotation and translation) of the vehicle by using techniques like visual odometry and Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM). At the same time, if there are georeferenced landmarks or designed anchor patterns in the view, the sensors can also estimate the relative pose with respect to the georeferenced points and consequently calculate an absolute position of the vehicle. In addition, the optical sensors have the environment perception capability, which can also be used for the function "Lane detection" and "Localize the vehicle in the environment" to localize the vehicle with respect to the surroundings.

The function "Get road-side messages and measurements" takes input from the communication module and parse/process the information obtained from the road-side infrastructure, e.g., georeferenced landmarks for the visual sensors. Literally, the function "Get local map data" extracts the local map data from the map database (optionally may also achievable from online database through communication links) for lane detection and automobile localization usage.

The measurements from the optical sensors are passed (after validations) to the function block "Estimate pose using visual measurements", and the block outputs the position and attitude estimation result with respect to a particular pose (either the pose of the vehicle in the past or some landmarks in the field of view of the sensor) using visual positioning algorithms.

The function "Estimate position using measurements from multi-sensor" takes measurements and single-sensor position estimates as input from GNSS and all the other sensors, and generate a unified solution through sensor fusion.

Any failure in the measurement or data acquisition in the multi-sensor localization module will result in unavailability of the corresponding data. The failure in position or pose estimation functions can be either availability/continuity issues, e.g., the algorithm fails to generate meaningful outputs, or integrity issues, e.g., the estimate is significantly erroneous. Depending on the situation, the MOBU may need to adjust the operational mode correspondingly.

4.4 INTEGRITY MONITORING MODULE

The other three aforementioned modules are related to the basic functionalities of the automobile MOBU. The integrity monitoring module (marked by red color in the design diagram) is mostly relevant to the safety and reliability of the navigation system, which is one of the most important core concerns in safety critical transportation applications.

The environment of the road traffic is significantly challenging for the navigation system. Compared with the conventional civil aviation, the GNSS receiver faces great performance challenges in applications like self-driving car, because of the complicated and changeful environments for road traffic. On the one hand, the challenges call for multi-sensor fusion solutions. On the other hand, the system must be able to monitor the output of different functions and detect ubiquitous risks, which becomes possibly more challenging with the introduction of multiple sensors and the sensor fusion methods. The MOBU needs to be able to monitor the correctness of the measurements from all the sensors as well as the results of the navigation estimation algorithms.

The GNSS measurements are tested against local threats on the receiver side by the function “Detect local threats to GNSS”. The local threat means the risk is not caused by the general signal-in-space error, but some local effects such as multipath and jamming. The AIMN also plays an important role in the GNSS integrity monitoring. The function block “Get augmentation and integrity data” parses the data received from the communication module, and output the information for improving the GNSS measurements quality while detecting outliers from the nominal measurements. This job is executed by the function “Validate and correct measurements”. Based on the information provided by the AIMN, the MOBU needs to validate the measurements from the GNSS receiver to ensure that the estimation algorithm does not take significantly erroneous measurements as inputs. Moreover, the accuracy can be improved by applying the augmentation data for better measurement quality.

The measurements from other sensors are also needed to be validated, the function of which are illustrated in Figure 12 as the block “Validate kinematic measurements” and “Validate visual measurements”. The measurements from different sensors can be used altogether for cross-validate errors in different sensors, and select the appropriate operational mode to process the multi-sensor measurements, which is executed by the functional block “Select Mode of Operation”.

Moreover, the function block “Detect faults in sensor fusion algorithm” tests the estimation result from the multi-sensor fusion positioning solution for FDE. If a fault is detected in parts of the measurements, the block provides feedback information to the estimation algorithm to exclude problematic measurements to recompute the position. Besides the fault detection and elimination, the MOBU navigation unit will also output some integrity information along with the positioning estimates, e.g., protection level or integrity flags, which is done by the function “Monitor positioning

integrity”. It should be mentioned that the multi-sensor integrity monitoring and fault detection is very challenging and is still lack of a standard procedure as mature as GNSS integrity monitoring. Nevertheless, it is an essential function for the safety critical autonomous driving application. One important perspective for HELMET MOBU is to investigate the possibilities to develop (part of) the multi-sensor integrity monitoring schemes as a foundation for further developments.

5. FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE DESIGN FOR UAV MOBU NAVIGATION UNIT

5.1 INTRODUCTION

In this section it is presented the functional architecture of the UAV system design and then the detailed functional description of UAV-OBU. The peculiarity of UAV aeronautical operations requests system solutions not always coincident with the other applications.

5.2 HELMET UAV SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND SYSTEM FUNCTIONAL DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

In order to better understand the UOBU functions and operations the overall system architecture is depicted in Figure 13 and Figure 14.

Figure 13: Overall UAV application system architecture

Figure 14: UAV Rail scenario with operational area constrained by virtual fences

As such the UAS/RPAS-PIT Station Highly Integrated System Network Segment within the HELMET infrastructure shall be composed of the following main functional Operational Elements, namely:

- 1) The Operating UAS/RPAS Center (UOC) which encompasses the Unmanned Aircraft (UA)/Remotely Piloted Aircraft (RPA) in a specific Configuration and Remote Pilot Stations (RPS) operating in LOS and/or BLOS mode by means of a Control and Non-Payload Communications (CNPC) Link (UP and DOWN Data and Voice Link) and Navigation Aid Components utilizing for this purpose a Terrestrial and/or Satellite based Network for Command, Control, Communications, Sense and Avoid (or Detect and Avoid) services covering all appropriate UTM airspace classes for railway and automotive related assets , in all integration cases and flight phases. This element shall include the operational services and capabilities provided by each PIT Station system but from this is excluded the UAS Logistic Support element.
- 2) The UAS dedicated PIT Integrated Logistic Support (ILS) Element (PIT STATION): which shall guarantee UAS/RPAS supportability, operational availability and safety throughout its Operational Life-Cycle.
- 3) The HELMET Augmentation Network Element dedicated to UAS/RPAS Ground and Aerial Operations (AMIN): this shall encompass the physical connectivity of the UAS/RPAS Navigation subsystem with the GNSS Galileo and potential Augmentation Services by the HELMET multi-modal Augmentation and Integrity Monitoring Network
- 4) The communication networks (UCN): we can distinguish the communication among the ground infrastructure to exchange data and commands up to the PIT station and the communication link among PIT station or by satellite/HAPS and UAV/RPAS.

For the scope of this study in the following will be not discussed the UAV control center while the PIT station functionality is provided in section 3.2.

The full Flight Phases' graphical presentation the UAV HELMET related missions (as described in detail in the document 2.2 CONOPS) is reported in Figure 15. The UOBU configuration depends on the UAS flight mission operative mode and profile, on the changes and adaptations of its operations,

on the way that interacts with the PIT station and the way that the PVT computation is performed and consequently on the positioning integrity verification approach.

Figure 15: UAV reference mission timeline and its operative modes.

Recalling the different UAV mission control typologies there are noted the various modes of selected operational modes, as follows:

Direct LOS

In this typology the operator controls the UAV in visual mode

- Direct via PIT station

Here the operator uses the optical equipment in addition of the on board accommodations to control the UAV. This is typical for landing and take-off phases

- BLOS via PIT station

The most innovative and challenging mode of operation. The operator supervises or controls the UAV via the PIT station link. Note that this link may pass via ground communication network or via satellite to allow the UAV to be safely controlled even in remote areas. In practice

- Autonomous

Possible autonomous operation will be mainly operated during the en-route flight phase while not excluding autonomous flight operations in the entire mission profile/phases if required by the operators soon.

The landing can be also autonomous with the support of a VBN system like what presented in Figure 23. As alternative in case of poor visibility a RF landing system may be implemented based of on board autonomous or on ground assistance.

Figure 16: Landing autonomous by optical support principle of operations.

In order to specify requirement for safety and operation it was adopted the concept of Performance-Based Navigation (PBN). PBN is a method of defining aircraft performance requirements independent of the specific equipment.

In other words with this approach we move from sensor-based navigation to performance-based navigation. This leaves the system designer free to select and even update equipment according to other requirements or simply to their life-cycle evolution (configuration upgrades and/or updates during the life-cycle of the equipment).

Then as already mentioned in the user requirement and CONOPS we refer to Required Navigation Performance (RNP) to define performance requirement in terms of accuracy, availability, continuity and integrity and are independent of equipment capabilities.

The HELMET architecture should provide a contribution to merge the different sources of integrity for improving mission and safety critical operations.

In order to improve system safety the following functions should be introduced according to literature (Sabatini et al.) but here extended in their meaning, in the overall system design:

- **Prediction (caution flags)**

Prediction is mainly based on Space augmentation but more on ground augmentation system that only can provide status in integrating navigation and communication safety of the area where it is placed. This allows a better plan of the UAS/RPAS mission and the overall UTM traffic management. One specific case might be that the PIT station could detect interference and communicate this situation to the operator station signalling the risk in entering in such areas or simply the PIT station could signal its malfunctions.

Prediction is applicable for instance to evaluate the flight path and identify potential areas where the GNSS signal is not effective or is disturbed.

The meteo data is also a key element and part of the mission planning, analysis and final authorization.

- **Avoidance optimal flights path guidance**

The availability of good integrity data allows to optimize flight path and to define potentially dangerous situation anticipating correction manoeuvring or flight reprograms. This of course in our

system based on UTM or ABS-B/PIT station but in the future with assistance of on-board S&A process.

- **Reactions (warnings flags)**

When a warning is detected, may be navigation signal is out of order or exists a potential collision danger, then an action should be performed. It is important to minimize the false warnings. The action may consist in a redefinition of UAV mission, trajectory or mode of operation just reconfiguring on board HW and SW.

- **Corrections (recovery path guidance)**

Corrections are needed in case of emergency situations. In this case it is important to have the correct situation awareness around the UAS/RPAS so as to optimize the required escape or avoidance manoeuvres.

For the time being this activity is done under the operator's supervision but could be fully automatized.

It is important to emphasize here the difference of actions in case of emergency wrt. other applications like Rail or Auto. If the communication links are lost or the navigation assistance is not supported, then the correction actions may consist of:

1. The UAS/RPAS autonomously (or assisted by local augmentation system or operator) land in a pre-defined area pre-planned before mission start
2. The UAS/RPAS remains in flight possibly loitering over a pre-planned area until it receives a definitive and/or unambiguous revised flight plan and/or path.
3. The UAS/RPAS is reprogrammed with new trajectory
4. The UAS/RPAS is reprogrammed in a redundant or degraded operation mode to conclude the mission

Depending on the status of communication and on board functionality action can be automatic or executed from the operator on pre-defined procedure that can start automatically to reprogram trajectory and send data to the UAV. In practice the operator just assists to the machine functioning. It is also necessary to identify potential mission classes because safety may vary:

- **Routine mission**

It may consist of a surveillance mission with flight path from a PIT station to another one. Basically, the mission is operated in a semiautomatic way with pilot supervision.

During this mission is however possible for emergency or needs change the flight path based on pilot control command.

The en-route phase requests not stringent accuracy requirement but very good integrity in particular when the UAV is operated in BLOS. The main recovery action is based on VBN assistance.

The routine mission definition, being repetitive, may follow a learning curve activity where ground feature are stored in an on board data base that is used as complementary on board navigation method. This can be very useful for PIT station automatic landing. The process can be portable and stored in other similar UAV performing the same mission. More in general in case of routine operation a dedicated activity will consist in geo localization of ground elements and point of interest that can be associated with maps. This activity can be also performed with a specific UAV operating with camera (even 3D) and PPK.

- **Specific/Critical operation mission**

In this mission a few flight phases will be automatic or semiautomatic (landing/take off, approach) but pilot takes control of the UAV for the specific operation time interval. In this mission mode the navigation accuracy is very important and should be sent to the operator screen in a short latency

time. In addition even the map should be referenced with high degree of accuracy so that the pilot can get a good awareness of relative position of UAV and target under observation.

- **Special mission**

These missions are devoted to specific activities that need pilot directly operating the UAV in loco. As for Bridge or galleries inspections where UAV distance from obstacles can't be guaranteed by autonomous or remote controls unless very sophisticated S&A mechanism are embarked. And additional external systems are implemented to facilitate the operation in those missions. Even in this case PIT station may play a role connecting additional equipment inside the gallery for operation especially in particular situations like the emergency's ones. However, this aspect will be not further discussed in this context.

For the scope of the Helmet work our effort will be concentrated on the first type of mission mode as described above.

The UAV in our application will operate in a "controlled" airspace with expected "exemption " from local Aviation Authority. Currently, rules vary from country to country and things are more difficult for manufacturers and operators. Nevertheless, such regulatory process slowly but steadily, is running to harmonize rules and procedures.

The main issues to cope with in the UAV application process deployment are:

- Autonomous mission management with human supervision where required and/or dictated by aviation safety issues
- Contingency /emergency management
- UTM/ATM system availability and reliable management
- System Health monitoring system (ground, on board, telecommunication)
- High navigation and communication integrity
- Certification of system and functions

For the time being it is proposed a study case of a UAV that will operate in semi-automatic way with pilot supervision that could be accepted for initial service experimentation interested institutional and/or private users. The UAV class taken under consideration is up the 25 Kg MTOM (Maximum Take-Off Mass) and below following the rules of:

"Specific" (medium risk) UAS/RPAS operation category that, considering the risks involved.

It requires an authorization by the competent authority before the operation takes place and considers the mitigation measures identified in an operational risk assessment, except for certain standard scenarios where a declaration by the operator is sufficient; this is achieved by communication each mission to ATM/UTM authority.

It requires a risk assessment, which should follow the JARUS Specific Operations Risk Assessment (SORA) methodology, performed by the operator. Thus, the Regulation in this category considers the following:

- a) Increased risk operations
- b) Safety risk assessment
- c) Approved by NAA possibly supported by Qualified Entities unless approved operator with privilege
- d) Operation authorisation with operations manual
- e) Concept of accredited body
- f) Airworthiness of drone and competence of staff based on risk assessment
- g) The CONOPS assumes that most of the professional flying in VLL will be considered Specific operations.

The integrity is (or should be) of high interest for UAV platform operators, as it might even be mandated when demonstrating compliance with future safety regulations. In this regard, two key statements define integrity: accuracy is below tolerances, and no faulty measurements are used.

To perform autonomous UAV missions Beyond Visual Line-Of-Sight (BVLOS) or in low-altitude airspace safely, achieving high accuracy and reliability of navigation solutions is required.

This motivates the development of a cost-effective local-area UAV network that utilizes a Local-Area Differential Global Navigation Satellite System navigation solution that in our case is derived from AIMN. The PIT station operates as bridge for this task and achieves a level of integrity comparable to that of Ground Based Augmentation System (GBAS) Category I operations by monitoring navigation faults at the ground station and by broadcasting integrity information to the UAV.

In addition, the PIT station will monitor the surrounding EM environment to identify potentially dangerous interferences. This is also a key feature in our operations in order to achieve the higher safety critical level possible.

PIT station/Helmet is designed to support UAVs with a minimum operating altitude of either 50 ft plus obstacle height (within 5.10 km of the ground facility) or 200 ft (within 20 km of the ground facility) by providing an accurate position solution and a tight uncertainty bound on its position error.

The utilization of a two-way datalink between the ground facility and the airborne user provides a major improvement in system flexibility. The two-way datalink enables the system not only to allocate integrity risk to each fault hypothesis dynamically to obtain the minimum safe protection level but also to simplify the geometry screening needed to mitigate ionospheric anomalies by computing the maximum error in vertical position only for the satellites known to be tracked by each UAV.

Specifically, each UAV can continuously send its GNSS measurements to the ground station, so that error corrections and integrity information can be generated also by the ground station just for this known satellite geometry. This information is then broadcast back to the UAV to allow it to compute its position solution. The integrity status of each UAV, including its current protection levels, is maintained by the ground facility and is used to guide each vehicle while maintaining safe separation from nearby obstacles and other UAVs. The architecture of this system involves space-conserving hardware configurations and several simplified GBAS integrity monitoring algorithms to reduce both the cost and the complexity of the system.

Despite the PIT station and its background infrastructure in our specific missions it is of paramount importance to embed in the UAV/RPAS a suitable on board integrity mechanism that can operate even irrespectively from SBAS and GBAS support with acceptable degree of safety.

So, other navigation sensors are required to provide reliable navigation in case of GNSS signal interference or blockage. In this study, the idea is to incorporate multiple sensors to assure complete UAV navigation system safety. In addition, even more parallel layer of integrity will be deployed and operated in function of the specific mission or mission phase as later described.

With the inclusion of multiple sensors, a new fault hypothesis, which is a multi-sensor failure, is added to the existing ground support integrity fault tree. The onboard module integrates Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensor output with the Ground Support solution using a Kalman filter (KF). In addition, optimal protection levels are computed by allocating the newly introduced multi-sensor integrity risk dynamically together with the Ground Support (combination of PIT station and Helmet central node) integrity risk.

The sensor failures depend on sensor type and quality. However a FDIR (Fault Detection Isolation and Recovery) module embedded in the system shall identify fault in the HW and SW and will be able to reconfigure the system even in a graceful degradation mode or initiate the recovery procedure in case of loss of communications link or position data.

An important requirement to fulfil is the estimation of heading that with a dual-antenna GPS receiver can be estimated with an accuracy of less than 0.5° . This system is much more reliable than a stand-alone magnetometer and corrects the typical sensitivity issues caused by electromagnetic sources like the UA/RPA engine through a continuous and automatic calibration of the magnetometer using the data provided by the dual antenna GPS receiver.

Finally, the issue of authentication both in the GNSS and communication signals is very important because it can generate a protection against the spoofing that can have dangerous consequences, in case of GNSS it can be managed at different levels:

- Open service message authentication
- Commercial authentication services (based on E6)

Important is also the possibility to authenticate the UAS/RPAS position and timing for different purposes such assurance but also for police and law enforcement assessment.

The system we are defining will embed the capabilities currently requested to operate in a safe way such as :

- Geo fencing

Virtual barriers will be defined for RPAS/UAV operations for instance along the railway lines

- Waypoint navigation

Those define the trajectory to be followed by drones from moving for instance from PIT station A to B.

- Geotagging

Geographical information, ground reference point and emergency locations will be loaded into the UAV on board avionic navigation system before each mission to improve safety and utilize information for camera or other sensors for navigation augmentation.

That ground reference information can be used for:

- Geolocalization of images
- Produce independent positioning information for safety, ie SLAM technique
- Produce relative, that is transform reference point into pseudo satellite and extract pseudo range equivalent to be introduced in the PVT processing in case of lack of GNSS satellites or their unavailability.

Other capabilities that the system architecture and the relative aircraft will embed are:

- Drone telemetry/tracking position reported to pilot via PIT station or satellite link
- Detect & avoid by additional sensors or ADS-B or UTM data. Basically, PIT station will embed a ADS-B sensor to detect UAV and /or Aircraft flying all around.
- Drone Identification: only identified aircraft will be authorized to fly in the future aerospace so our system will communicate each planned mission to UTM just before initiation.
- Recovery actions will be planned and setup every mission by :
 - o Return to home
 - o Altitude hold
 - o Loiter on an area

So it is proposed to implement an OBU that:

- Improve small UAV capabilities, resilience and integrity and permit their operations even in BLOS and in autonomy.
- Introduce a multilevel positioning computation based on the integration of GNSS and optical processing. The possibility to further add additional localization provided by passive utilization of ground communication networks, for instance 5 G, can be also explored.

In addition in order to improve safety as said before it is possible to anticipate situations of a complete loss of GPS signal using the integrity information included in SBAS messages or compute this information on ground and transmit it to the RPAS and pilot and take some countermeasures. SBAS-capable receivers can use the integrity data included in SBAS messages to calculate the so-called protection limits which are related to the reliability level of the GNSS measurements. Basically, we can have different situations:

- GNSS data are reliable and can be integrated by satellite augmentation EGNOS. These results can be integrated and complemented with ground data to improve reliability, integrity and accuracy
- Same situation as above with additional data from ground (differential, PPP-RTK) to get needed accuracy for the specific application
- Satellite augmentation (EGNOS) signals are not being received from the EGNOS satellites so the corrections are not being applied to improve GPS positioning and there is not an integrity service for calculating the protection levels. However the ground augmentation data are received and replace EGNOS data.
- GNSS signals are not reliable enough. This is detected when the protection levels are higher than user-fixed alarm limits that are set depending on the application. In this case the avionics should state if on board sensors can support degraded navigation accuracy for completing mission or enter in correction or recovery action.
- GNSS can provide a number of satellites less than 4 then the optical processing provide the complementary pseudorange by optical processing of reference points.
- GNSS receiver is not able to calculate a position solution then the optical processing is used according for instance to a SLAM technique

So the main concept here is to use integrated integrity information (space & ground) to detect degradation in GNSS signal and anticipate to a possible loss of a GNSS position solution.

For this purpose, it is necessary to identify new states in the on board avionics, communicated to pilot and UTM, that lead to enter in dedicated operative modes of RPAS avionic.

However, in principle in case of loss of communication link the UAV, if autonomous operation is enabled, is still capable to operate in highly safety condition because of GNSS ABIA integrity and combine optical and GNSS processing.

The modes and the HW states will be defined based on the values of the protection levels and the stated alarm levels. When the protection levels are higher than the alarm limits, then GNSS signals cannot be reliable and the autopilot may decide to try to land the aircraft before further signal degradation or even complete signal outage is experienced. In order

It is worthwhile remember that the UAV/RPAS particularly in the BLOS operation should withstand inside and AIR traffic system that present risks and challenges same consideration are given in D 2.2 and 2.3.

The basic idea is to communicate every mission trajectory to the UTM and embark an ADS-B transmitter in order to communicate UAV position.

The UAV System will follow the UTM principles even with additional points:

- Only authenticated operations will be launched
- Avoid impacts among any other UAV entering in the georeferenced air space
- Avoid impacts with aircraft entering in the georeferenced air space

- Avoid exiting from mission planning operation unless emergency or replanning activity with immediate communication to UTM
- When initiated and during mission operators should have awareness of any constraints from traffic and all kinds of environments
- Keep Public safety as priority wrt any activity.

In this contest the UAV operator station should be able in collaboration with UTM centre:

- Recognize proximity alert (based on GEO fencing, etc)
- Recognize intruders (via ADS-, UTM or other sensors)
- Management of contingency alert
- Replan flight in 4D for emergency management
- Manage priorities

The management of priorities should also embed in the PIT station network control.

UOBU integrity general consideration

Position and navigation integrity issues

Integrity is defined as the system capability to produce alerts when system position accuracy degrades below a predefined threshold.

Classic (A)RAIM computes HPL and VPL or the minimum error that can be detected however other integrity mechanisms should be investigated for UAV flying at low altitude and in areas where SIS can be blanked. But as it will be later described RAIM can't operate in case of GNSS signal degradation and an additional form of integrity is needed, the ABIA.

Other capabilities will be derived from optical and mw applications. Such georefencing by imaging or complementing with "imaging pseudo satellites" or using for instance 5G stations as signal of opportunity for locations.

Current SBAS/GBAS play an important role in improving navigation performance both in terms of accuracy and integrity. However, it is fundamental to design and implement a properly designed on board integrity system that can introduce a safety critical standard in UAV applications in precision approach and landing.

So the idea is to explore the concept of integrated space, ground and on board architecture where Helmet can provide essential services.

The on-board unit (OBU) design and functions is conceived to cope with the different missions and phases of flight in order to comply with the specific current requirement in terms of accuracy/integrity with a layered configuration that allows timely failure detection and system reconfiguration.

For the time being as said in this study the design of OBU operation is limited to the en-route mode.

Communication integrity issues

Moreover it should be recognized the key importance of communications for bringing the augmentation ground data to/from the UAS/RPAS. Clearly the integrity, availability and continuity of communications should have even better performance of the GNSS itself in order to be effective.

This link can be either a line of sight (LOS) air-ground (AG) link between the two entities or a beyond line-of-sight (BLOS) link using another platform such as a satellite or high-altitude platform (HAP). Data rates for such links are expected to be modest (e.g., a maximum of 300 kbps for compressed video, which would not be used continuously).

In this respect another important function of GNSS is to provide data for the ADS-B equipment that likely will be mounted in same configuration in all the future system if operated in BLOS.

The ADS-B can provide the useful information for UTM. This can provide for instance sequencing and de-conflict constraints (see landing), flight plan/mission objectives, separation assurance and collision avoidance and of course environmental constraints.

In this case it is important to evaluate if the augmentation data that we derive from HELMET can be transferred via the C2/3 link or by a dedicated additional link.

The communication link is a general key issue of UAV/RAPS operation completely different from the other applications where we have autonomy or pilot seated in the vehicle.

Communication loss is even more critical than EGNSS data or integrity degradation and can leads to immediate recovery actions. It is a common practice that if the radio link is lost, then the autopilot commands the aircraft to go to a predetermined waypoint (what is commonly known as Return-To-Home (RTH) or Return-To-Base (RTB)).

5.3 UAV POSITIONING MAIN SUBSYSTEMS FUNCTIONAL DESIGN

5.3.1 OBU

General Description

The UOBU is an avionic subsystem based on the combination of several equipment and units in order to provide the aircraft the position, velocity and timing needed for operation in the different operative modes and situations.

There are several key aspects of UOBU design in the UAV operations related to safety, reliability and trajectory optimization in conjunction of:

- Required Navigation Performance (RNP)
- Required Surveillance Performance (RSP)
- Required Communication Performance (RCP)

And in addition, the DAA (Detect and Avoid) operations in conjunction with the most general UTM and ATC/ATM are key issues in UAV system architectural design.

Predictive detection of errors sources, provided by PITStation/AIMN, can allow optimization of trajectories and substantially improve system safety.

Integrity augmentation refers to a suite of methods used to detect GNSS error sources and alert in case navigation error exceeds a certain predefined safety limit.

The methods to monitor integrity are based on GBAS or SBAS systems however alternative integrity methods are needed for UAV/RPAS when they operate at very low altitude. This because there the errors are dominated by multipath and antenna masking as opposite to what happens in aerial flight. Therefore, here is explored the integrity concept based on ABIA (Aircraft Based Integrity Augmentation) that can assess GNSS data integrity and report to the on-board navigation system. Nonetheless ABIA is integrated with ARAIM in order to cover all the needs.

On the other hands the legacy integrity approach and system will be kept operative and used when flight operations will allow in a overall view of optimizing resources, safety capability, redundancy of sources at more levels and get the best in terms of accuracy.

Moreover, at system level, the presence of PIT stations introduces an additional layer of safety by monitoring EM environment and detecting potential threats for UAV operations both in terms of navigation and communications.

In this contest the primarily effects on GNSS integrity are:

- Signal losses: that can be generated from different factors (Atmosphere effects, attenuation, scintillation, Doppler effect, etc.)
- Antenna Masking: because of operational environment
- Multipath: again, generated from surrounding environments and from aircraft surfaces/structure.
- Jamming: intentional or unintentional

The conventional SBAS and GBAS can't provide mitigation of the above effects and therefore it is needed to adopt suitable on-board arrangement to cope with those effects.

The basic position computation equipment is the GNSS receiver that is combined with a IMU and optical cameras.

In addition, in order to improve accuracy and integrity data from SBAS and GBAS are acquired, processed and integrated.

As said the basic integrity concept here applied is the ABIA that provide two warnings (Sabatini et al.):

Caution Integrity flags: is the predictive alert of the system that a GNSS fault produces an imminent violation.

Note that in our system design caution integrity flags are also produced by the PIT station

In fact, the PIT station can analyse the EM spectrum and in case of potential problem can communicate to the remote operator (or directly in a future fully autonomous system) the local critical situation for the suitable recovery action. In case of autonomous operation is the UAV itself that take the actions and depending on the specific situation decide whether proceed or re-plan the mission.

Warning integrity flags is the detection of integrity lost and therefore request corrective actions. Those can be of different typology depending on the mission operative mode.

On- board internal integrity flags: is the health and operation status of the OBU provided to the on board mgmt.

In addition to the above legacy flags that are devoted to the signals and environment status and health, it is added another flag (in reality a status vector) that is based on internal unit status of health and correct operation. System the awareness of HW and SW status even in case of system configuration as function of mission mode or reconfiguration in case of detected failure. The FDIR function can be implemented by a SW, HW or a mix of the two.

Concerning the on board operation the integrity functional flow is depicted in Figure 17 where the UAV mgmt. system included in the UOBU receive the integrity flags and takes decision based on the integrity management system.

Figure 17: Critical Condition report flow

In the integrity process there are two situations: the misleading information is not detected, or it is not sent in time to the systems for decision and action.

Then TTA is the maximum time interval allowed between integrity risk detection and UAV/system/operator is informed.

For instance, in case a caution flag is issued the MMS (mission management system) can act on the OBU function giving more precedence to alternative sensors like IMU or optical imaging.

TTA (Time To Alarm) definition in ABIA:

- TTC (Time To Caution): minimum time to detect unsafe conditions in the GNSS operations
- TTW (Time To Warning): maximum time allowed from GNSS fault condition to detection and signalling

Of course the subsequent action initiated by the on board control will be different also according with the UAV control mode and status (pilot, autonomous, ground connected).

The TTA is a critical item in the system safety critical issue assessment and should be compliant with the system requirement.

According to the nature of the flag and the relevant status word produced by the FDIR module the On board computer takes action and commands the recovery action to the OBU or to UAV

Block diagram

In Figure 18 the OBU functional block diagram is provided.

Figure 18: UOBU and associated navigation function block diagram

The Figure 19 provides a more detailed picture of the various functions and operations implemented in the OBU and their relations.

The OBU design is quite complex because it should withstand with the safety critical requirement from the block diagram a few of the main functional subsystems:

- **Communications**
In this design the communication links are controlled by the UAV On Board Main Computer.
- **PVT navigation**
The PVT SS includes all the equipment and SW needed to get the UAV position, velocity and timing.
- **Integrity**
Integrity SS includes all the equipment and SW needed to assess system integrity
- **Optical**
Optical SS includes all the cameras and processing SW to produce imaged and data needed for integrity and PVT SSs.
- **FDIR**
FDIR SS include SW and HW needed to assess OBU correct operation and reconfigure it depending on mission and status
- **DAA**
Detect and avoid SS includes units and algorithms devoted to support UAV operations in the air space.

Figure 19: Avionic integrated integrity functional block diagram according to ABIA principle and legacy standard ARAIM.

OBU operative modes

Figure 20: OBU operative modes

In Figure 20 the UOBU operative mode flow chart is presented.

A synthetic description of modes is given here below:

- OFF: OBU is switched off
- Warm UP: in this mode the OBU is switched on and a BITE function is run in order to verify unit's health status
- GMI (Ground Mission Initialization): in this mode the mission data are written in the OBU memory and sensors are calibrated.

Figure 21: GMI operation example

- **FLIGHT OPERATION:** OBU is fully operative and act according to the command transmitted by the on-board control computer and navigation system. It contains the different sub-modes that are performed. A few of them can be carried on with the support of PIT station.
- **RECOVERY MODE:** this mode is acted when the FDIR function identify a fault in the OBU operation HW or SW. this mode should not be confused with the warning flags that are generated by the OBU as consequence of integrity analysis.

The recovery mode is devoted to set the redundancy or the graceful degradation status and communicate the new OBU status and performance to the onboard computer for taking any further actions.

For the purpose of this study in the following only the en-route operation mode is dealt with.

- **GME (Ground Mission Ending):** this mode is run after the landing and consists in several action including the dump of mission data when those are not transmitted during the mission and the telemetries reporting.

The modes can change also depending on the UAV control mode that can be pilot assisted or autonomous as described in D 2.3.

Here it is conceived a mission where only the mission phase is pilot controlled while the other modes are pilot supervised.

Then in order to support the study objectives the mode en-route is considered operating in autonomous mode with or without the PIT station.

For the applications where non real time very high accuracy is requested, we intend to follow the PPK approach for what concern accuracy augmentation. indeed only DGNSS can be enough for en-route operations. This is done both for simplification and the reduced needs of communication BW between the UAV and the PIT station. So even the smaller UAV can be operated or there a better utilization of the UAV operation assigned BW. In case of critical missions, the UAV is directly controlled by the pilot.

	Sensor SN	Sensors Kinematic	Sensor OPT	RAIM	ABIA	SBAS	AIMN/PIT S
01 ASSIST	GNSS	KMT	-	Y	N	Y	Y
02 ASSIST	GNSS	KMT	-	Y	Y	Y	Y
03 ASSIST	GNSS	KMT	OPT	N	Y	Y	Y
04 AUTON	GNSS	KMT	OPT	Y	Y	Y	N
05 ASSIST	-	KMT	OPT	-	-	-	Y

Figure 22: possible combination of OBU sensor operations

In the table of Figure 22 the combination of sensors that can contribute to the PVT have been identified in combination with the integrity approach and the augmentation system.

OBU Functions description

An aircraft navigation system combines the information from the on board sensor suit to determine and manage the following information:

- Kinematic information (acc, & angular rates, etc)
- Navigation states
- Trajectory and track parameters
- Internal self status

Basically, the aircraft operates on the basis of external reference data but can also flight for same time and occasion in death-reckoning even from one reference point to another. This may happen in case GNSS signal is lost and on the basis of optical processing localization and kinematic sensor the UAV.

In the next section the description of each OBU subsystems is given.

PVT Navigation functions

Figure 23: PVT subsystem functional block diagram

In Figure 23 the PVT subsystem functional block diagram is depicted. It is possible to identify:

- The GNSS receiver antennas

Basically, it will be mounted on the top of the UAV structure possibly with attention to limit the multipath that can be auto generated. In principle would be possible to calibrate the multipath but during manoeuvring the configuration change so in this case would be better to protect the receiver

with same shield. On the other hand superior antenna performance in terms of polarization signal reception and low gain at the lower incidence angle guarantee same multipath intrinsic rejection. The antenna specifications reference are in the following given as derived from existing commercial products:

- Receive: GPS /Galileo L1, L2,
- GLONASS G1 G2,
- BDS B1, B2, B3 band signal
- Working mode: GNSS multi-mode combination mode
- Operating voltage: 3.3-10V
- Antenna size 120 mm*75mm*37mm
- Connector form TNC header
- Waterproof grade (Waterproof, grade) IPX7
- Connector form TNC
- **weight : 200g**

(Frequency Range)	1555MHz~1615MHz/1198MHz~1278MHz
(Impedance)	50Ohm
(Polarization)	(RHCP)
(Axial Ratio)	<3dB
(Elevation Coverage)	360°
(VSWR)	≤2
(Gain of Antenna)	4dBi
(LNA Gain)	35dB±2dB
(Noise Figure)	≤2.0dB
(VSWR)	≤1.5
(VSWR)	≤1.5
(Gain Flatness)	±1dB
(Pout at 1dB Gain Compression Point)	≥0dBm
(LNA Drain Voltage)	3-15VDC
(LNA Current Consumption)	≤40mA
(delay)	<5ns

structural characteristics :

(Dimension)	120 *75*37
(RF output Connector)	TNC
(Mounting Method)	Screw mounting
(Waterproof Grade)	IP67
(Shockproof Grade)	IK08

working environment :

(Operating Temp.)	-40°C~+85°C
(Storage Temp.)	-40°C~+85°C

The GNSS receiver

The GNSS receivers for UAV already exist and are available from different manufacturers like Ublox. It will be a two frequency multi-constellation receiver with SBAS correction internal capability.

In principle it should be preferred a fully SW solution because it is more flexible to be adapted to new upgrading.

What is important is that the GNSS receiver provides in out the so called observables that are very useful for integrity monitoring (ABIA & RAIM). Not all the receivers do that.

For what concern interference most of current receiver already own protection mechanism that for instance can detect CW signals and blank them. Then the specific GNSS processing based on spread spectrum/correlation can in practice cancel most of those simple interferences. Of course nothing can be done against a white noise disturb that saturate the receiver. By the way another important issue to cope with interference, out of a nulling or steerable antenna, is to select an high dynamic receiver with at least 8 bits in the ADC.

The interference detection can be done at two levels (see Figure 24):

- Pre- correlation: looking at signal spectrum in input and its dynamic
- Post-correlation: looking at position, carrier phase, tracking noise, C/N0, etc

Figure 24: interference detection

Those considerations will be later recall when the integrity issue is discussed. Note that the receiver produces its PVT data also directly that sent to the MOBC. This for different reasons but in particular to allow a safety recovery status in case all the other OBU electronics fault.

Figure 25: COTS GNSS receiver also with embedded IMU

- The accuracy augmentation

In order to improve the current receiver position availability and introduce the AIMN correction it is conceived the module in Figure 23 under dotted box that is composed of:

- The masking/augmentation module

By this module it is generated the mask to select the satellite that can be allowed to participate in the PVT processing.

The mask is elaborated from the mask produced on ground by the AIMN center and the mask produced by the optical SS. This last is used to detect the satellite in visibility and discharge those received due to multipath.

Then the augmentation data can be derived from SBAS or better than AIMN. The MOBC decide by assessing the communication link what data should be used.

- The GNSS data processing module

It introduces in the GNSS data the masks and the augmentation data that are sent to the PVT processing module.

- PVT processing module

This module be based on different algorithm, here it is conceived as an extended Kalman filter that are as input:

- GNSS data /pseudo ranges
- Kinematic data from kinematic sensors
- Optical pseudo ranges from camera
- Weights from integrity function

For the time being the fusion is based on a direct approach but also a complementary mode can be enabled in case of failures. Prediction residuals are used to separate error sources but also for integrity.

The three last module can be integrated in one single processor such ARM Cortex or similar.

The weights data in input are elaborated by the integrity module in order to increase or decrease the importance of sensor input in the PVT processing. This will depend on the analysis of external environment, data from sensors, their status, and ground data.

- Kinematic sensor suit

This is generally formed by gyro, accelerometers and barometer for the altitude. The magnetic compass should be placed in a suitable position as far as possible from the other UAV equipment because of the well known magnetic sensitivity. The adoption of an altimeter if embeddable in a small UAV could be a good option.

In the market it is possible to find very good integrated sensor suit with good performance suitable for the UAV applications and often integrated with the GNSS receiver. The IMU will be based on MEMS components that have high long-term drift and therefore need of periodic calibration acted by GNSS position. For gyro $1^\circ/\text{h}$ accuracy is expected.

Miniaturized altimeter or simply terrain detector can be also found very useful for landing.

- Timing and frequency generator

A key role is also assigned to the timing generator that is fed by a TCXO oscillator and is synchronized with the GNSS PPS. The signals so generated constitute the basic reference timing for all the UAV system and for MOBC. Note that HELMET is kept synchronized to the GNSS timing.

Integrity

As said the total navigation error should withstand inside the assigned thresholds (HAL/VAL) and the integrity monitoring system must be able to detect faults that leads to hazardous or misleading data.

In other words the Integrity is the capability of a system to predict/ detect degradation of the positioning accuracy below a pre-defined threshold and then consequently initiate a real time operation to conduct the system in a safety critical status with a recovery of navigation performance. Of course this loss of integrity can come from the reference position systems (i.e. GNSS system) or by errors and faults in our system. So it is important to get aware of our system operability and healthiness even before to assess measurement integrity.

In fact not always it is possible to restore the system full performance and in absence or degraded sources of absolute positioning or redundant units/sensors the system will operate in a so called graceful degraded mode or simply not operate at all. In order to achieve that scope it is defined a multilevel approach

The integrity will be acted at four levels integrated and supervised by the FDIR function:

Level 0: Verification of all the data/equipment operation that enters in the PVT Navigation module (i.e. Kalman filter) and in the integrity validation.

Level 1: Comparison of results from different sources (optical, mw, ect) and external integrity assessment.

Level 2: Verification of consistency of residuals out of navigation unit filter against prediction (RAIM, etc).

Level 3: Check integrity flags internal and external as previously discussed.

In Figure 26 the integrity process that leads to recovery action for both caution and warning flags. This process is in line with the safety requirement of 10⁻⁷ as for relevant table and document D2.3.

Figure 26: integrity functional block diagram

In Figure 27 the interface of integrity on board system are shown. In particular it is pointed out the presence of the warning messages that can be generated internally from the sensors analysis or from the FDIR function or externally by the combination of PIT sensors, HELMET core centre and UTM centre.

The RAIM is used to verify the integrity of the selected satellite combination and to compute the HPL/VPL.

Figure 27: overall avionic based integrity functional system interfaces

In Figure 28 the main functional components that participate in the decision process related to assess integrity and in case that is not compatible with the specific flight phase then a recovery action is adopted.

Figure 28: integrity and FDIR computation process on board

The core of the signal integrity is based on the ABIA, supported or replace from the ARAIM when the UAV fly in an environment and mode free from impairments.

The ABIA consists in the analysis of the main causes of GNSS signal degradation that are not accounted by RAIM and that are:

- Multipath

There are several ways and algorithms to detect and mitigate multipath. We are proposing the skyline detection by optical processing as alter described. However, a classic algorithm can be embedded too.

- Obscuration

This mainly depends from surrounding environment (cities, gallery, trenches) and from aircraft manoeuvring. The obscuration invests also the communication link that might loss up to 30 dB.

Also this aspect is supported by the optical processing.

- Poor C/N₀

The C/N₀ are extracted from the GNSS receiver and are indicators of performance and integrity.

- Doppler

In case of aircraft fast manoeuvring the doppler can be too high for the system managing and cause misleading.

- DOP

The DOP plays an important role in the GNSS accuracy it is well know that it impacts as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = K * \text{UERE} * \text{DOP}$$

- Interference/ jamming

This aspect has been previously dealt with.

In Figure 29, derived from the literature, it is possible to read the current definition for the thresholds of the above integrity parameters. The CIF (Caution Integrity Flag) and the WIF (Warning Integrity Flag) are those referred in section 2.

Type of CIF	Criteria	Type of WIF	Criteria
<i>Masking</i>	When the current aircraft manoeuvre will lead to less the 4 satellite in view, the CIF shall be generated.	<i>Masking</i>	When less than 4 satellites are in view, the WIF shall be generated.
<i>Satellite visibility</i>	When one (or more) satellite(s) elevation angle (antenna frame) is less than 10 degrees, the caution integrity flag shall be generated.	<i>Satellite visibility</i>	When one (or more) satellite(s) elevation angle is less than 5 degrees, the warning integrity flag shall be generated.
<i>DOP</i>	When the $EHE_{3-\sigma}$ exceeds the HAL or the $EVE_{3-\sigma}$ exceeds the VAL, the CIF shall be generated.	<i>DOP</i>	When the $EHE_{2-\sigma}$ exceeds the HAL or the $EVE_{2-\sigma}$ exceeds the VAL, the WIF shall be generated.
<i>Multipath</i>	When the ELP exceeds 0.1 radians, the caution integrity flag shall be generated.	<i>Multipath</i>	When the multipath ranging error shows a sudden increase with the A/C flying in proximity of the ground (below 448.5 metres), the warning integrity flag shall be generated. When the multipath ranging error exceeds 2 metres and the aircraft flies in proximity of the ground (below 500 ft AGL), the warning integrity flag shall be generated.
<i>Tracking loops</i>	When either $42.25^\circ \leq 3\sigma_{PLL} \leq 45^\circ$ or $0.2375T \leq 3\sigma_{FLL} \leq 0.25T$ or $0.05d \leq 3\sigma_{DLL} \leq d$, the CIF shall be generated.	<i>Tracking loops</i>	When $3\sigma_{PLL} > 45^\circ$ or $3\sigma_{FLL} > 1/4T$ or $3\sigma_{DLL} > d$ the WIF shall be generated.
<i>C/N₀</i>	When the C/N ₀ is less than 26 dB-Hz the CIF shall be generated.	<i>C/N₀</i>	When the C/N ₀ is less than 25 dB-Hz the WIF shall be generated.
<i>Jamming</i>	When the difference between the received (incident) jammer power (dBw) and the received (incident) signal power (dBw) is 1 dB below the jamming to signal performance of the receiver at its tracking threshold, the CIF shall be generated.	<i>Jamming</i>	When the difference between the received (incident) jammer power (dBw) and the received (incident) signal power (dBw) is above the jamming to signal performance of the receiver at its tracking threshold, the WIF shall be generated.
<i>Doppler</i>	When the C/N ₀ is below 28 dB-Hz and the signal is lost, the caution integrity flag shall be generated if the estimated acquisition time is less than the application-specific TTA requirements.	<i>Doppler</i>	When the C/N ₀ is below 28 dB-Hz and the signal is lost, the warning integrity flag shall be generated if the estimated acquisition time exceeds the application-specific TTA requirements.

Figure 29: thresholds definition for caution and warning flags

Optical processing function

The optical subsystem is presented in Figure 30. There are two cameras foreseen in the design, one with WFOV dubbed Polifemo and a second one called NFOV camera. Then a processing unit devoted to process the camera images into data useable for OBU positioning and navigation contribution.

Figure 30: optical processing subsystem functional block diagram

The basic Polifemo camera is shown in Figure 31 it has a very huge FOV in elevation (+70°/-40°) and in the centre there is an aperture that allows the accommodation of a GNSS antenna. So the idea is to combine the optical view of the camera with the GNSS data in order to get:

- Multipath mitigation
- Antenna obscuration awareness
- Identification of pseudo satellite based on optical processing
- Sky vision on 360° azimuth for awareness and obstacle identification
- UAV speed computation

Optical camera will adopt the SLAM technique. As an example the Scale-Invariant Feature Transform can be applied to tracking landmarks and create 3D maps.

It is of importance to provide to the processing equipment the heading or the orientation of the UAV in order to geolocalize the maps or the images that are transformed into pseudorange or masks for GNSS. Note that maps are stored in the SS memory before mission begin but can be updated during flight.

From the requirement point of view the fundamental parameter is the GSD (Ground Sample Distance), it depends from a combination of camera characteristics and the geometry by which images are collected. The following general formula is applicable where Pix_H is the number of pixels, FOV_H is the horizontal FOV and R the distance from ground.

$$GSD_H = 2 \tan \left(\frac{FOV_H}{2Pix_H} \right) R$$

However, camera performance includes the capability of object discrimination related to recognition detection and identification of a target. The MTF is a parameter that takes into account most of camera impairments.

The processing unit should be based on an FPGA ad hoc developed because of the processing load but the new COTS processor in commerce today embeds a multiprocessor and an area of the FPGA that can be programmed via firmware.

Figure 31: the innovative Wide FOV camera proposed for this study.

The camera has been designed from INAF research officer and produced by Lobre (It). It is proposed also for integration in automotive and space applications (rovers, star trackers, etc). Advantages of the system with respect to others off-the-shelf or custom panoramic monitoring systems are:

1. A unique image sensor is used to monitor the entire panoramic field of view plus an enlarged part of it.
2. An unique data flux is present both for panoramic and enlarged views, which simplifies the data transfer management.
3. Low weight: only one lens and one sensor are used.
4. There are no moving parts (no failure points, no motor, no power consumption, etc...).
5. The simplicity of the optical head also reflects on low cost.
6. The optical head is easily replaceable in case of glass breaking.

The current prototype is based on the design presented in Figure 32.

Subsystem	Info	Note
BPL	Manufactured by Lobre srl company (Brescia, IT)	

Image Sensor	Sony IMX264 CMOS. Basler acA2440-35 uc	5 Mpx
ACQ Board	Odroid-XU4, Samsung Exynos5422 Cortex A15 + Cortex A7 Octa core CPUs, 2Gb RAM, eMMC.	
Storage	MicroSD flash	Storage @1 fps
Power supply	CD-CD converter: out 5 Vcc, 7-15 V	About 1 A @ 12V
WIFI client	Mini router/gateway TPLink WR702N	Working up to 5 fps
Remote CTRL	Ctrl via web I/F @ static address 192.168.4.121	

Figure 32: Polifemo demonstrator characteristics

Concerning the bottom camera in the detailed design will be selected a suitable COTS among those already available.

There is the option to embark two Polifemo cameras one looking at the top and one looking at the bottom the last embedded with a High Resolution sensors used for landing and same accurate GEO reference of imaging and consequently position.

Figure 33: conceptual system based on two WFOV cameras with integrated the GNSS antenna on the top and HR lens on the bottom for optical navigation assistance

The optical subsystem must provide:

- Obscuration/masking maps

Those maps are used for mitigating the multipath effects on GNSS positioning but also for navigation and sky monitoring.

Figure 34: optical processing imaging

Note that the image in Figure 31 are achieved with a fisheye lens while Polifemo lens has a much higher field of view.

Imaging processing step for the WFOV camera for error mitigation may consist of:

- Image simplification with optimum contrast
- Pixels classification: open sky or obscured sky (building, etc.) by proper classification algorithms
- Compare and recognize with suitable maps if available or complete counturnig the area
- Analysis with GNSS antenna position and attitude and satellite ephemerides data base obtained by GNSS rx or ground segment

Imaging processing step for the WFOV camera for optical pseudo satellite detection.

- Image simplification with optimum contrast
- Research in the data base reference points or combination of, suitable for UAV localization
- Compute relative position and UAV speed
- Transform data in a format suitable for merging data with GNSS data

The second-high resolution camera is used for landing assistance and geolocalization based on georeferenced points. An interesting solution may consist of colouring the rail sleepers with a code such that can indicate the UAV position. Of course, this idea in case of snow should be complemented by other special arrangement in the sleepers (ie heater).

In Figure 35 an example of the processing needed for UAV landing on the PIT station is represented.

Figure 35: image processing for landing

FDIR

The FDIR (Fault Detection Isolation & Recovery) function could be allocated in one of the OBU processor, in case of a multicore CPU one of it could be used to run the routine.

The FDIR module collect all the status telemetries of the OBU and the integrity Flags and sends a report to the MOBC. Refer to Figure 24 for the overall picture of system safety aspects. In case failure are discovered the MOBC can command OBU in the recovery mode and FDIR set the new OBU status before re-entering in the normal modes even with depredated performance.

Communication Functions description

The overall UAV communication model is reported in Figure 36 for the Control and Non Payload Communication (CNPC). It deals with all the aspects of UAV communications and control including the Air Traffic.

It is important to keep in mind that in case of UAV in the civil air traffic the communication are even more important that the positioning and navigation.

Note that for the large UAV is now under study the possibility of CNPC operation by satellite when in BLOS. But this can be done only for large UAV that can embark a suitable space transponder.

The introduction of the PIT station equipped with a space transponder allow even the smaller UAV to be commanded remotely via satellite. From another point of view it is possible to think the PIT station connected to the UAV control centre both via ground and space links with additional system safety in BLOS operations.

Figure 36: UAV Communication model

The CNPC communications includes all the TT&C links between the UAV and the remote pilot. In addition, the link is used to support DDA operation for system safety and video in case of landing/take-off.

The link is also used to transfer all the navigation augmentation information to the UAV OBU to improve accuracy and integrity of GNSS data.

Generally, this link is characterized by low data rate, half or full duplex, high integrity and safety.

The second link is devoted to transfer to ground data from the on board sensor. This link is characterized by medium/high data rate and is basically unidirectional.

The communication block diagram is presented in Figure 37.

It is composed of two commercial receivers in UHF, L or S BW. ITU common frequencies in L band are: 405-425 MHz; 915 MHz; 1,39-1,45 GHz. Then there are the S band and the C band.

Note that the 5030-5091 MHz is the new BW for integrated ground and space communications. They are working in warm redundancy and interface directly with the main on-board computer (MOBC).

The augmentation data are extracted from the communication stream and sent to the OBU for processing. Then the MOBC tx to the PIT station or user the status and position.

The MAPS are stored on board in the PIT station by a specific wireless interface or directly using the communication subsystem.

Figure 37: Communication subsystem block diagram

The communication protocols will be standardized.

The link from the PIT station includes a few sub-sections devoted to:

- commands from Pilot or approaching equipment's
- navigation augmentation and integrity assistance
- mission data (ie maps,...)
- mission payload

The MOBC transmit to ground:

- status telemetries
- navigation data

Major communication requirement is:

- **UAV/PIT stations C2 full duplex**

C2 and augmentation data rate:

Up: 10 Kbits/s

Down: 300 Kbits/s

BER: 10⁻⁵

- **UAV/Pit station data (unidirectional)**

Down: 1-2 Mbits

By HGA antenna

All the links will be characterized by high degree of integrity achieved by encryption authentication and acknowledge.

The loss of a data link must be addressed by a link-loss procedure. It is important that the aircraft always operates in a predictable manner. From the survey, it was revealed that the most common link-loss procedure is for the aircraft to fly to a predefined location. Once at the predefined location, the UAS can either loiter until the link is restored, it can autonomously land, or it can be remotely

piloted via secondary data link and/or redundant main data link at cold or semi-hot condition(s) (Depending on the RPAS category, complexity and operational/mission capabilities).

For additional secure communication proof, one approach is for the UAV to acknowledge or echo all commands it receives. This will ensure the operator that all commands sent are received and acknowledged. Such an approach will also notify the operator if the aircraft receives commands from an unauthorized entity.

In case the commands can be simultaneously received from both BLOS and LOS links, a priority setting will define priorities.

DAD

Detect & Avoid functions can be implemented with a wide number of different sensors in a cooperative and non-cooperative approach here in the on board are composed of two just elements:

- ADS- B tx
- Optical camera

The PIT station is equipped with a ADS-B receiver and transmit data to UAV and UTM control centres.

New system typologies seen a very high integration between GNSS and ADS-B equipment.

The UTM in a air crowded air space depends at most by the accuracy and integrity of the aircraft position spread all along.

Figure 38: ADS-B equipment for UAV on the left; complete DDA sensor suit on the right

As example of incoming technology in Figure 38 the pingRX Pro, announced from uAvionix, a detect-and-avoid ADS-B receiver for professional unmanned aircraft systems (UAS). pingRX Pro detects private and commercial aircraft operating on 978 MHz and 1090 MHz. The received aircraft's identity, position and altitude are visualized on a moving map in real time, allowing the UAS operator or autopilot to remain well clear.

5.3.2 PIT station

Description

PIT station general description

PIT station consists of a ground Station/Terminal characterized by a UAV landing areas and a number of equipment including sensor and communication unit to support the UAV missions.

PIT stations will be deployed all along the mission path at a suitable interdistance such to allow the complete coverage of the mission areas.

Figure 39: PIT station functions

The PIT station functions (Figure 39) are:

- Deployment capability in any anthropic or remote areas with limited environmental effects
- Landing (augmented and automated) site with wireless refuelling/recharging station for electrical UAV
- Direct communication in L ,S or C bands with UAV (TBD)
- Communication relay for space and ground C2/3 communications
- Communication relay for space for mission data tx in Ka band
- GNSS local integrity station (including interference monitoring and position accuracy augmentation) with communication messages in contact with HELMET augmentation station
- Local data processing and storage
- Local access to LOS UAV control
- Support for ATMUTM by ADS-B rx
- Provide georeferenced site for optical navigation augmentation sensor
- Internal BITE and autocalibration capability
- Local capability to connect directly an operator to a UAV

Figure 40: PIT station functional block diagram

PIT station equipment/systems (Figure 40):

- EGNSS tri frequencies antennas
- Omnidirectional communication antenna
- High gain directional antennas
- ADS-B antenna
- WIDE FOV optical arrangement for surrounding and landing areas monitoring
- Satellite antenna (optional)
- Remote communication network modem

The PIT stations by omni antenna will be capable to:

- Fix communications by the omni antenna that operates on dedicated frequency channels, that change cell by cell
- determine the UAV position by its GNSS data
- determine frequency value, frequency doppler, power levels of the link with UAV
- based on above points to send the link characteristic to the steerable antenna and UAV to initialize the operative connection

A steerable antenna in a first assumption is devoted to control only a single UAV.

The key parameters are:

- Latency
- Frequency and relative BW
- Data Rate
- FEC

The PIT station main communication requirements are:

- **PIT station-intra network (with operator)**

Data Rate: 100Mbits/s bidirectional

QoS: selectable with minimum latency (<100msec) in case of emergency
BER: 10-7 (10-9 for non-emergency data)

- **PIT station Satellite**

For C2

FWD: 10 Kbits/s

RETURN: 300 Kbits/s

For Mission data

FWD: 10 Kbits/s

RETURN: 10 Mbits

By dedicated space antenna vs GEO satellite.

PIT Station data to Helmet core centre

- EM status
- EGNSS local rx data

PIT Station data to UTM via Operator station

- Local visibility status
- ADS-B data

PIT Station data to Operator station

- PIT station health status
- All the data acquired by its sensors

As option local radar for UAV control will be implemented in critical areas- The PIT station can also determine the UAV heading by connecting the PIT station antenna with the UAV antenna as for Figure 41. The PIT station internal receiver computes the heading also with support of UAV gyros.

Figure 41: determination of UAV heading by combined processing of PIT station and on board GNSS Rx

OBU Implementation and RAMS considerations

While in Rail and Auto and large UAV systems there is room, weight and power enough to implement complex SIL system with votation, control and redundancy in the small UAV there aren't so much embedding capabilities.

Moreover, let's consider that traditionally fault tolerance systems are operated in a static fault tolerance approach combining multi sensors architecture and simple fault detection. In the new UAV aircraft, it is possible to identify more sensors (ie inertial sensors) dispreads all along the structure. One example max consist in the IMU that is included in the OBU but likely replaced in the UAV navigation electronics.

Then in order to satisfy the safety requirement occur a well-tailored design that exploit any possible system capability overlap and functionality to permit first to determine and evaluate integrity then to continue operations in an alternative or degraded mode. Fortunately, the current components are really miniaturized.

In terms of reliability of the HW it should be accounted that the duration of a single fly is between 30 m to 1 hour in case of more powerful UAV. Then a BITE is launched at the beginning of each mission so the probability of a fault in flight is di per se low.

Then form a configuration point of it is conceived to not redundant any sensors but only the MOBC and the communication link.

The OBU can be configured with a redundant processor in a cold or warm configuration.

In case of cold configuration, the UAV motors should be configured to continue to operate during the processor switch-on.

For what concern the OBU itself it is possible to conceive two "low cost" solutions.

One (Figure 42) is composed of two similar computer for processing. The first is devoted to compute PVT and data integrity the second implement integrity verification and FDIR.

In case one computer fails the remaining computer takes care of the all functions so guarantying same safety to the system operations.

Figure 42: OBU configuration based on to similar computers

Figure 43: OBU configuration based on two parallel computers and a controller

In Figure 43 the OBU is implemented by two computer chains working in parallel and one controller. Clearly due to the lack of redundancy in case of failure only one computer will remain, but this is a way to reduce short time risks. In a long time the configuration is less valid and a cold redundancy should be preferred.

In Figure 44 the FTA for the combination of PVT computation based on the design presented in the previous section is reported. The major importance for UAV consists in the internal capability to determine position with adequate degree of integrity and safety. This means both to have integrity mechanism but also a redundancy in the system position determination for comparison and replacement.

From the safety point of view in Figure 45 the FTA for the UOBU integrity & safety is provided. Quantitative analysis will be performed during the detailed design.

Figure 44: FTA based on the PVT computation modes

Figure 45: OBU- PVT FTA.

In Figure 46 OBU safety is viewed for the HW consistency point of view. In this case the FTA doesn't account for the system resilience due to the capability to provide PVT even when some of the units failed.

Finally in Figure 47 the FTA for DDA. This function is essential for UAV operations in a semi or fully automatic mode and respond to the safety requirement. The GNSS position accuracy and integrity is part of the game being the position information broadcasted and received from the UAV and PIT Station. All the information are sent to UAC^{AV} and UTM control centres. In a future in a fully automatic system the UAV will be able to modify its trajectory to avoid collisions.

Figure 46: OBU HW FTA

Figure 47: DDA FTA

6. REFERENCES

- [1] RTCM, RTCM 10403.3, Differential GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite Systems) Services - Version 3, RTCM, 2016.
- [2] RTCM, RTCM 10410.1 Standard for Networked Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol (Ntrip) Version 2.0 with Amendment, RTCM, 2011.
- [3] A. Neri, R. Capua und P. Salvatori, „High Integrity Two-tiers Augmentation Systems for Train Control Systems,“ in *PNT 2015*, 2015.
- [4] J. Saastamoinen, Atmospheric Correction for the Troposphere and Stratosphere in Radioranging of Satellites, in the Use of Artificial Satellites for Geodesy, Geophys. Monogr. Ser, 1972.